

PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL ASPECTS OF EPOXY MATRIX

FORMATION FOR HIGH PERFORMANCE FRP

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There are many organic and inorganic fibres with high strength and Young modulus. But there is still no possibility to realize their high mechanical properties when producing composites (FRP) with polymer matrix. Formation of composites with maximum high mechanical properties is limited now by the properties of polymer matrix. Among great variety of polymers which are used as a matrix for high performance composites the best results according to their mechanical properties are by now achieved with epoxy resins of various types.

The available theoretical information on the structure of three-dimensional polymers does not allow to understand those peculiarities of such polymer structure which make it impossible to achieve its high strength. This problem is the most important scientific one for the creation of high performance composites with polymer matrix.

Investigations of the correlation of structure and mechanism of formation of different epoxy matrixes cured with aromatic amines on one hand and their mechanical and deformative characteristics - σ , ϵ , E , etc. - on the other hand are being performed in the Institute of Chemical Physics of the USSR Academy of Sciences.

To solve this problem the search of systems - epoxy oligomer and curing agent - subject to form the network with the close to ideal structure has been done. The thorough kinetic study of curing reaction has shown that under certain conditions it becomes possible to perform this reaction in such a way that the by-processes have the negligibly low rates. Separation of individual products at different reaction stages has proved the conclusions of the kinetic analysis.

The networks formed under such conditions have really occurred to be rather homogenous. Thus the measurements of density fluctuation in a sample by the light scattering patterns have shown that the latter are about $10^{-2} + 10^{-3}$ and correlation radius $r_{\min} \approx 5000$ - 8000 \AA and $r_{\max} \approx 25000 \text{ \AA}$.

One may suppose that the obtained with such systems homogeneity is the principal peculiarity of networks formed according to the polycondensation mechanism, unlike the networks which are cured according to the polymerization mechanism (for instance, the unsaturated oligoetheracrylates).

An important characteristic of a network is the conversion of reactive groups as it is cured. This value is specially connected with any mechanical property of a network. The maximum possible value of conversion on network formation has been discussed theoretically for the two-dimensional model. The structure of polymer matrix in such model is considered as the statistical set of cyclic molecular formations with certain distribution of cycles according to their size. Calculation of distribution has been performed by the Monte-Carlo method. Analysing the given structure at different stages of its formation process the information has been obtained on the possible threshold degree of curing, rigidity, high-elasticity modulus and other important parameters.

Such approach permits in principle to establish the connection between the chemical structure of the initial oligomer and the curing agent with the topology of the network formed.

Serious attention has been also paid to the role of curing regime of the given system for the formation of certain strength and deformative characteristics. It has occurred that these characteristics are independent from the temperature - time way of the process on condition that the possible complete conversion of reactive epoxy and amine groups is achieved in all cases.

The principle and very important question is the formation and structure as well as the physical-mechanical characteristics of the matrix in composites.

Investigations of the curing reaction kinetics in the presence of the reinforcing glass fibres have shown that for different epoxy resins one can observe both the strong dependence of the curing kinetics (rate decrease) and the independence on the presence of a filler. Measurements of the kinetics of adhesive joint formation of the epoxy polymer matrix to glass fibre (adhesive strength) well coincide with the curing reaction kinetics. But even when there is no influence of glass fibre upon the kinetics of network formation reaction, the structure of the latter differs from that in bulk. Electron microscopic pictures of polymer matrix at different distance

from the glass (from 2 to 22 μ) show that the lining influences the structure of epoxy network at distances up to 5 μ . We are now undertaking attempts for the direct measurement of mechanical characteristics of epoxy networks in micronic layers. However one should overcome the serious experimental difficulties when working this problem.

The curing reaction may influence also the strength of the very reinforcing elements of the composite. Thus the strength of glass monofibre with protected surface decreases during the network formation reaction by 15%.

All these peculiarities surely significantly influence the composite final properties.

The molecular level approach to the theoretical modelling of network structure is now the only possible one, because there are not any physically proved models of supermolecular structure of such systems. Nevertheless there exist some facts which show that the formation of strength and deformative properties of epoxy networks is significantly influenced by the processes occurring at the supermolecular level of their organization.

An example of such phenomena is the fact of the strength anisotropy of polymer epoxy matrix under the action of tension upon it during the curing process. The strength of the completely cured sample in directions parallel and perpendicular to the stretching axis differs by 30%.

The prolonged exposition of the completely cured samples at different temperature-time regimes always results in marked changes of their properties: strength and elasticity pass through a maximum (which points to the existence of optimal duration of curing) in a time which is by a power of ten greater than that of complete conversion; loss of sensitivity of the initial slope in $\sigma - \epsilon$ diagrams of cured samples with the rate of deformation; change of strength dependence character with the rate of deformation, etc.

The elaborate study of all these phenomena should assist to the development of scientific principles of polymer matrixes creation for high performance FRP.

INTRODUCTION

The formation of high performance filament winding composites with the polymer matrix includes the search and development of such matrices that would facilitate combined performance of filament winding in the material which permits to fully realize high performance properties of the latter. The existent theory permits the connection of elastic, tensile and deformative properties of the

matrix which make the composite with the given filament winding high performance.

However, at present there is no theory that would permit a priori to choose the chemical type of a polymer and the method of the matrix formation to obtain the necessary properties of the composite. As is well known the experience accumulated by the composite makers in the world (2,3) makes it possible to choose the chemical type of the polymer that would provide the necessary properties. For example, high temperature composite matrices must contain in its structure heterocyclic fragments with rather developed system of conjugated bonds. The best high performance composites are made from epoxy polymers. These results are empirical and now it is not altogether clear which particular properties of chemical composition, structure etc. of epoxy matrices lead to such specific features.

It must be emphasized that this fact is not to be astonished at since it fully reflects the situation present in polymer science. Despite successes in physics, mechanics and structure analysis of polymers there is no even qualitative theory that describes the connection structure-properties even for linear polymers. This is the more so for three-dimensional polymers, the investigations of the properties and structure of which and the laws of their formation lag behind as compared to linear polymers.

However, the demand for polymer matrices for high performance composites is growing steadily which is due to the appearance of commercially available new types of winding materials with very high elasticity and strength. Among them are various single crystal "whiskers", new types of high strength glass fibres, carbon fibres and, especially, high modulus organic fibres (4). The search for new matrix types for these winding materials is widely spread and is rather successive despite the empirical basis on which the matrices are chosen.

However, in the profound study of the matrix problem one of the main problems is the question of the basic cause that leads to better properties of one type of matrix as compared to another.

That is why in the Ac.Sci. of the USSR have begun wide investigations of the structure, properties and processes of formation of three-dimensional polymer networks that are good matrices for composites. Most various matrices are being investigated, among them - polyester, phenolformaldehyde and epoxy polymers. But now my report is limited to epoxy matrices.

For the particular case of epoxy polymers we thought it necessary to turn our efforts to the establishment of the principles which control the formation of the structure, elastic, strength and deformation properties at first of a pure matrix and then of a composite. In this we based on theoretical conceptions of chemical composition and reactivity of initial components and mechanism of curing.

One of the first steps was to develop a statistical model of the structure of three-dimensional polymer which would permit to trace back the connection between the chemical structure of the initial oligomer and the curing agent and topology of the produced network and its physical and mechanical properties.

The statistical model has been based on the assumption of the network structure of the polymer as an aggregate of randomly linked cycles with certain distribution of sizes.

The model was developed for the particular chemical system diepoxide $\text{V}-\text{R}-\text{V}$ - aromatic diamine $\text{H}_2\text{N}-\text{Ar}-\text{NH}_2$. For this model the following classification of cycles is introduced (Fig. 1). The works on the modelling of structure, properties and the curing process can be divided in two directions. First is the kinetic one based on the statistical kinetics of branched chain reactions in the process of the network formation. In this case the values analyzed are usually conversion α of the curing process with time and gel and sol fraction content.

The second direction is the analysis of mechanical properties of an "ideal" network on the molecular level. Under the term "ideal" we understand the structure made of equal size cycles.

Unfortunately, these two approaches are loosely connected with each other.

We set before us a task of creating a model that, though to a first approximation, would permit following the curing process on the one side, and on the other - calculating some mechanical characteristics (elastic modulus, strength) at any conversion of the process.

Fig. 1 presents the first terms of the series of cyclic structures. The cycles are classified by two indices i, j , the first index characterizing the size of cycles, while the second determines the configuration of a cycle which depends on the mode by which diamine molecule enters the cycle. Thus, the topology of a network structure can be characterized by the distribution function $W(rij)$ and the first and the second moments of distribution M_n and M_w .

Strictly speaking, the introduced distribution function $W(rij)$ does not fully describe this set of cycles, since it does not take into account various modes of connecting the cycles with each other. However, to a first approximation we restricted our consideration to this distribution function $W(rij)$. (See next page).

It should be emphasized that the process of filling up the vacant knots can be cut at any moment. This fact permits following the kinetics of the formation of the model network.

The network structure was generated on a plane hexagonal periodic lattice in the knots of which tetrafunctional diamine molecules

 were placed. Bifunctional epoxide molecules were randomly attached to the knots. The formation of cyclic structures during condensation reaction and their linking into single branched system was modelled by the statistical Monte-Carlo method on a computer.

Condensation process of the attachment of diepoxide to diamine was modelled in the following way. Bifunctional diepoxide molecule attached by one of its ends to the knot may then randomly attach to one of its 6 immediate neighbours. This attachment process proceeds until either all the vacant knots are occupied or all bifunctional molecules are used. The algorithm of the formation of network structures allowed us to vary a great number of parameters which determine the kinetics of their formation: probabilities of primary and secondary joining to the knots, lattice type, number of dimers and monofunctional diluents in the system. Apart from this, we took into account the probabilities of intermolecular cyclization that leads to the formation of single cycles, weakly connected to the network. Thus we analyzed a large series of structure diagrams.

Basing on the analysis of the generated structure diagrams, numerical distribution functions $W(r_{ij})$ were plotted. Immediately analyzed parameters were number-average M_n and weight-average M_w degrees of polymerization of the cycles in the network. The number of partly linked and free dimers was also calculated.

Fig. 2 presents typical diagram of the structure obtained at stoichiometrical ratio of dimers' and knots' functionalities. It is clear that, despite stoichiometric, composition of the system monodispersity of the distribution of the distances between the knots and randomness of the formation, the network is inhomogeneous and consists of weakly linked parts.

Fig. 3 presents diagrams of the structures obtained with the introduction of internal cyclization. It should be pointed out that in this case some places in the network structure (NS) remain vacant. Analysis of the structures obtained on various lattices (tetragonal, hexagonal) with various cyclization probabilities have shown that in each case the limiting conversion of functionalities is 94 - 96%.

Figs. 4 and 5 present distribution functions and the first and second moments of these functions obtained from NS with different concentrations of dimers in the system. The diagram for this case is presented in Fig. 6. Deviation from stoichiometry leads to a more friable NS and the appearance of large cycles in the tail of the distribution function. This, in turn, leads to a sharp increase of M_w . The presence of cyclization reactions also leads to a sharp decrease of the connectivity of NS.

To estimate the possibilities of the proposed mathematical modelling of the polycondensation curing of epoxy resins, we studied the chemical structure of gel and sol fractions of the cured resin.

The mechanism of the curing process for the chosen system had been investigated earlier. The parameters of the reactions were taken into account in the model. Gel fraction was analyzed from the number of unconsumed epoxy groups in the network, sol - from the number of diepoxide molecules in it. Experimental and theoretical results presented in Fig. 7 confirm the assumptions of the model. It should be emphasized that the theoretical value of the limiting conversion is confirmed by these experiments. This result shows that the absolute completeness of the curing process is statistically impossible.

The proposed method permits also modelling the mechanical properties of a three-dimensional polymer.

Fig. 8 presents the results of such modelling. The model allows the calculation of elastic modulus and strains of NS bonds in order to compare them to the real values. As seen from Fig. 6, inhomogeneity of NS leads to the presence of a small number of overstrained bonds which is seemingly the reason for the low real strength of polymeric networks.

To correlate between the structure of the network and the mechanical properties of epoxy resins, we studied the influence of the network structure on dynamic modulus and glass temperature of some cured epoxy compounds. The structure was changed in the experiments by the introduction of corresponding amounts of diepoxide and monofunctional diluent.

Figs. 9 and 10 present the dependence of viscoelastic modulus on the concentrations of diepoxide and monofunctional diluent in the system. The curves show that the modulus decreases sharply with deviation from the stoichiometry which is explained by the decrease of the connectivity of NS. Basing on experimental results and data of the structure analysis we obtained a correlation dependence of viscoelastic modulus on the number - and weight-average degrees of polymerization of the cycles in the network. Linear dependence that is shown in Fig. 11 indicates that the topology of the network can be directly related to the viscoelastic modulus. The model approach makes this dependence quantitative.

In the glass state an anomalous dependence of the elastic modulus on the network density have been found. With deviation from stoichiometry the modulus increased and mechanical loss decreased (Fig. 12). In addition to that, the viscoelastic modulus that characterizes the connectivity of the network decreases, which fact evidences it becoming more friable and the appearance of large cycles in the network structure. The less connective network probably has its molecules more densely packed which leads to the increase of the modulus in the glassy state. On the basis of this we can propose that hardness of the cured polymer is largely determined in the glassy state by intermolecular interactions.

Measurements of glass temperatures have shown that they are maximum in the polymer with a slight excess of diamine. Deviations from this amount of diamine lead to a decrease of glass temperature. As we have already mentioned, in the stoichiometrical system about 5% of partly linked diepoxide molecules are present. Since these molecules are rather flexible, their mobility is freed at temperatures lower T_g which leads to a marked increase of the free volume in the system. This facilitates segmental mobility in the system and lowers the glass temperature. Introduction of the excess amount of amine leads to the disappearance of unbound diepoxide molecules in the network. This increases glass temperature until weakly bound amine molecules appear in the network structure.

Fig. 13 presents the dependence of glass temperature on the percent amount of unreacted epoxy groups. The dependence is seen to be linear which speaks in favour of the proposed treatment.

The above facts permit the conclusion that the proposed model describes not only the formation process and structure of three-dimensional polymer, but also its physical and mechanical properties.

The second part of my report deals with the analysis of chemical kinetics of curing reactions in the systems of diepoxides and diamines $\text{R}-\text{R}$ + $\text{NH}_2-\text{Ar}-\text{NH}_2$. One of the main problems in the kinetic investigations is choosing the best curing conditions to reach maximum strength, elastic and deformation properties of the matrix. The same aim was in view in the kinetic investigations of the matrix formation in composite.

But, before starting kinetic investigations, it was necessary to choose chemical substances that would satisfy one important condition - that is, "purity" of the chemical process. In other words, we had to find diepoxide and diamine molecules that would react with each other with minimum by-processes.

It is known that from the chemical point of view the reactions of amines with epoxides is essentially studied and can be represented by the following scheme:

In cases of diamines and diepoxides each of the tertiary nitrogen atoms becomes the knot of the network. However, numerous by-reactions are possible in this system that would essentially violate the network structure through decrease of the number or the change of the structure of the chains and also polymerization of epoxy groups in the presence of tertiary amines.

The reaction products were analyzed by thin layer chromatography. It was established that in the sensitivity limits of the method ($\sim 10^{-11}$ mole) reaction between aromatic amines and diepoxides in temperature range $50^{\circ} - 90^{\circ}\text{C}$ gives only two products: one or two epoxides attached to aniline molecule.

Kinetic analysis of the reaction has shown that the ratio of the rate constants of first and second addition (K_2/K_1) is about 0.08. It is a very important result. The close values of rate constants shows that the decrease of first addition products activity owing to steric hindrances is insignificant.

The cyclization reaction has been studied with $\text{E}-\text{R}-\text{E}$ + aniline, where $\text{R} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_4$ meta- and ortho-. In the first case of meta-form during reaction in bulk of stoichiometric quantities (according to the number of functional groups) of initial agents the product average-number molecular weight strictly corresponds to the number of end-groups independent of temperature and reaction time, which points to the impossibility of cycles closing at one nitrogen atom of aniline. At the same time the ortho-system results in cyclic structures formation even on performing of reaction in bulk, the amount of cyclic structures being not less than 20% (according to the number of molecules; the average size of a molecule is in this case about 600). The resulting low molecular cycles are seen from topological models to be the least beneficial from the point of view of the network polymer structure. Thus it is obvious that the $\text{E}-\text{R}-\text{E}$ diepoxide reaction with aromatic amine $\text{NH}_2\text{-Ar-NH}_2$ is in principle acceptable as regards the "purity" of its performance, and it can be a good model for building the "ideal" net from the chemical (but not structural) view point. In case of aliphatic amines the situation is absolutely different. Here the reaction proceeds by many ways resulting in formation of a series of by-products.

The second part of this work is dedicated to the kinetic study of the process of net polymer matrix formation resulting from diepoxide reaction with aromatic amines. The kinetic study of such processes is really necessary because of many reasons. First of all from the purely scientific aspect, this study makes it possible to compare results of a real process of matrix formation with the statistical model of a network discussed before. Secondly, the kinetic study of real systems will permit not only to perform the complete mathematical description of the cross-linking process but also to prove the approaches of selection of temperature and time regimes of composites curing to achieve the high performance properties.

Besides that the knowledge of the process mechanism is the basis for the rational selection of a system to cure. The kinetic scheme of a process in diepoxide-aromatic amine system is given in Fig. 15. It can be seen from this scheme that in spite of the absence of side reactions the whole process is still rather complicated. Some peculiarities of the process should be mentioned not discussing the details of kinetic analysis:

a) The curing reaction proceeds with auto-acceleration as the resulting during the process on each act of the epoxy cycle opening OH-groups (reaction...of scheme 14) accelerate the process.

This should be considered when calculating the reaction heat. The high rate of heat liberation in composite at the maximum rate of the curing chemical reaction may result in overheating of the real object and as a result of that in the decline of some exploitation properties.

b) The sharp decrease of the reaction rate at high conversions is usually discussed as being connected with diffusion hindrances. Nevertheless it has been successfully shown that complexing of secondary hydroxyle groups with different electron-donating components of the system (epoxy, ether-group, primary, secondary and tertiary amines) also results in reaction deceleration.

It yet occurs that the maximum conversion of curing still amounts to 96% of the total number of functional groups (as it follows from the statistical model). This conversion is easily achieved even in case the reaction proceeds at temperatures less than the glass transition one for the three-dimensional network with the given conversion of curing (α). It means that diffusion hindrances do not create significant obstacles to the curing reaction completion.

It may practically occur that at some sufficiently low curing temperature, lower than some $T_{critical}$, the curing reaction completely stops thanks to the shift of chemical equilibrium to complexing. Thus the full conversion of network curing will not be achieved and as a result of that - the necessary mechanical characteristics of a matrix will not be obtained. All chemical and thermodynamic parameters of chemical reactions according to the above process scheme are given in Table I. Knowing these parameters as well as the thermo-physical constants of an object to be cured, one can calculate:

a) conversion (α) of curing reaction with time as well as in any point of this object;

b) temperature in any point of the object.

Having the values of α and t^0 with time and space, it is possible to select the optimal regime of curing of the composite as regards the minimum internal tensions in the object and maximum mechanical characteristics of the matrix.

The route of curing of a given system and its influence upon the achievement of high performance properties of a matrix has been thoroughly studied. The detailed investigation of a network mechanical properties at high conversions has shown that the maximum σ^{lim} tensile and ϵ^{lim} at room temperature can be achieved in the vicinity of network maximum conversions (α) and their values are independent of the curing temperature regime (stepwise, smooth, etc.) on condition that reaction proceeds in the uniform temperature field within the object (absence of overheating).

The extensive study of matrix properties and selection of matrices, as regards their mechanical and deformative properties, is the necessary but far not sufficient condition of the development of scientific principles of creation of high performance composites on the basis of these matrices.

To create such composites it is necessary to know the laws of formation as well as the properties of a matrix directly in a composite, and also the peculiarities of matrix-reinforcing fibre interaction. Our information in this field is rather modest. Nevertheless the importance of this problem is obvious.

At present it is well known that many properties of a matrix in a composite differ from those in a pure bulk of a matrix. Thus in case of the studied diepoxides with aromatic amines as curing agents all this can be seen directly from the electron microscopic photos made in the Ukrainian Institute of Polymer Chemistry. The replica photos of epoxy matrices cured with aromatic amines at different distance from the reinforcing glass fibre are given in Fig. 16. The matrix structure has been exposed by its etching in plasma of an oxygen outelectrode discharge. Etching of matrix makes it also possible to approach to the glass for different distances.

It is seen from the picture that the average size of globules, their shape and distribution over the surface are different at different distance from the glass (a - 2μ , b - 10μ , c - 16μ and d - 22μ). It is not really surprising as the matrix network in the composite is being formed under specific conditions of a very thin layer whose physical properties are possibly greatly influenced by the interface.

In some cases the matrix curing reaction rate in composite also "feels" the surface of glass fibres. Deceleration of the curing reaction rate by 2.5-4 times in comparison with that in pure bulk of the same epoxide has been observed on curing of some diepoxides. It can easily be seen in Fig. 17.

Not less important for the composite final properties is the question of the kinetics of the adhesion bond formation between matrix and reinforcing fibre in the curing process. The slow, in comparison with the matrix curing time, formation of adhesion bonds is known to

result in its not optimal value. In the same way the too quick matrix-fibre reaction may result after prolonged composite heating in the decrease of adhesion strength owing to the degradation processes in the vicinity of fibre surface. Both phenomena may only assist to the destruction of composite under load. The scheme of a method of adhesion strength measurement is given in Fig. 18 (here the glass or steel fibre of 150 μ is threaded through an aluminium cup and then the polymer in the cup is cured to a certain conversion; after that the fibre is pulled out, adhesion strength τ is measured, which is equal to the shear load divided by the splice square). To prevent polymer bending in a thin layer the metal strap is applied.

The kinetic curves of the adhesion bond formation during the curing reaction are given in Fig. 19. For diepoxides cured with aromatic amines it occurred that the kinetics of adhesion bond formation well follows the kinetics of curing reaction, which is surely the other advantage of the diepoxide-aromatic amine system.

There obviously exists the opposite phenomenon: the polymer matrix influences during the chemical curing the glass fibres, which reinforce the composite. At high temperatures as the matrix is cured on the pure intact surface of glass fibres the decrease of their strength from 360-380 kg/mm² down to 330-350 kg/mm², that is by 10-15% is noticed. These experimental data are obtained on oligomer curing at a monofilament. Mechanism of this phenomenon should be further studied. The possible reason for such decrease is the matrix chemical interaction with the glass surface. It is also possible that some mechanical reasons (the appearing stress field in the elementary reinforced cell) are responsible for the above phenomenon. But the phenomenon itself is of great interest and its nature should be cleared up.

IV.

The last part of the present report deals with the quite principle at present fact that the molecular level is now the only possible one when modelling the structure and physical properties of a network. This fact is dependent on the absence of any physically proved models of submolecular structure of net matrices.

Nevertheless the limitations of only molecular approach is already obvious. Several factors directly point to the existence in a network of some processes, which occur after the complete conversion of amine and epoxy functional groups in a matrix. Some of these processes possibly occur at the submolecular level of polymer matrix organization.

To be short only some of them will be mentioned.

1. Anisotropy of strength of epoxy matrix in the uniaxial strained state develops on its curing. Film samples are cured in the

uniform temperature field up to conversions 80-85% at $t = 150^{\circ}\text{C}$ and then are strained by 2% at the same temperature. The further curing of samples is performed directly in the jaws of the testing instrument. Measurements of σ_{tensile} of cured samples have shown that σ_{11} is parallel to the tensile axis and, on average, is by 36% more than the same value but measured transversely to the tensile axis. The effective elasticity modulus E_{11} is in this case also by 24% higher. Besides that both values σ_{11} and E_{11} are by 27% and 18% correspondingly higher than the strength and modulus of non-strained samples.

The strain of the completely cured samples conducted at temperatures even higher than the glass transition temperature never results in the change of their properties or in development of strength anisotropy. The processes of molecular orientation in the three-dimensional network can be hardly imagined, and thus the study of this phenomenon is of great interest.

The following phenomena have been discovered:

The standard procedure is the prolonged heat post-treatment of composite objects. Such treatment which usually continues for a long time after the complete conversion of all epoxy and amine groups in a system, presumes the stabilization of strength and deformative properties of an object. It is also necessary for the completion of all relaxation processes in the cured matrix. Such treatment at the elevated temperatures in case of glass reinforced filament winding composites ranges as a rule between several and 10-12 hours.

When studying the properties of epoxy matrices, cured with triethandiaminotitanate, in the course of their heating at $t = 150^{\circ}\text{C}$ these have been noticed the marked changes of their properties on exposures, much longer than the standard time of heating.

Some results of these investigations are given in Fig. 20. Curve 1 shows the rate of heat liberation (calorimetric measurements) in the curing reaction. It is well seen that the complete conversion of epoxy and amine groups occurs by the 4th hour. The chemical analysis of epoxy groups by this time really proves their complete absence. The theoretical amount of heat Q which should be liberated at the given contents of functional groups in this sample just corresponds to the square under curve 1 for 3.5 hours with good accuracy. It is yet typical that liberation of heat continues for a very long time, although at a very small rate. The latter becomes equal to zero by about 100-110 hours.

Curves 2 and 3 show the changes of tensile strength and tensile elongation on heating (tests at room temperature). It can be easily seen that both values pass through a maximum during about 40 hours. Correspondingly the Maxwell's equation parameters-logarithmic viscosity and logarithmic rate modulus (curve 4), describing the relaxation processes in a matrix, proceeding in the elements of different

scale, become also stable by the 40th hour. The increase is about 30% which is surely the significant contribution to the given value.

The further decrease of σ and ϵ values (after 40 hours) is obviously because of the degradation processes. Matrix heating in air really results in some shift of maxima to the shorter time.

One can suppose that some processes of matrix reorganization at molecular and submolecular levels occur during heating. Processes at the submolecular level of matrix organization do really take place, which can be proved by the electron microscopic investigations of matrices cleaves. In a heating time the developed submolecular structure with clear boundaries between the separate oval-globular formations (their diametre is about 300-400 Å, Fig. 21) is scouring, the boundaries between elements become less clear. The absence of the developed surface relief under ionic etching points to the increase of structural homogeneity of a sample.

Chemical processes at the molecular level are also possible, in particular, the formation of ether bonds through the secondary chemical reactions between -OH groups. Some quantity of water, escaping on heating of samples, has been found.

It is yet difficult to give any substantiated interpretation of the above mentioned facts. Nevertheless they all point to a certain degree to the existence of phenomena and processes, caused by the reorganization of matrix structure after all amine and epoxy functional groups are spent.

Today our knowledge on strength, elastic, deformative and relaxation properties of polymer matrices are rather poor. The real composite constructions and objects serve at temperatures lower than those of glass transition of polymer matrix, which fact increases the contribution of intramolecular interaction to the above mentioned mechanical characteristics. At present we cannot describe the real network structure and as a result - the intramolecular interactions in net matrices.

Solution of such problem for matrices in bulk and in composite seems to be one of the most important directions of investigations, along with the study of regularities of matrix net formation in real composite.

TABLE 1

Oligomer	$k_{10}' \cdot 10^3$ l/M · sec	E_1' Kal/M	$k_2' \cdot 10^3$ l/M · sec	E_2' Kal/M	ΔH Kal/M	ΔS Kal/M · g ^o
ЭД-5	$1,1 \pm 0,2$	$9,4 \pm 0,5$	$5,5 \pm 0,2$	$9,8 \pm 0,5$	4,6	13,0
ЭД-6	$1,6 \pm 0,2$	$10,0 \pm 0,5$	$5,3 \pm 0,2$	$10,4 \pm 0,5$	4,7	12,5
ЭД-16	$1,2 \pm 0,2$	$9,5 \pm 0,5$	$5,3 \pm 0,2$	$10,3 \pm 0,5$	4,6	12,3
Э-41	$1,1 \pm 0,2$	$9,7 \pm 0,5$	$5,4 \pm 0,2$	$10,5 \pm 0,5$	4,8	13,0

Kinetical and thermodynamical parameters of the curing processes for diepoxides and aromatic amines.

FIG. 1 The cyclic structures

FIG. 1a The fragment of hexagonal lattice

FIG. 2 The structural diagram without single cyclization and with stoichiometric ratio of components

FIG. 3 The structural diagram with a single cyclization

FIG. 4 Distribution function of cyclic dimensions

FIG. 5 Number average $M_n(1)$ and weight average $M_w(2)$ degrees of the cycles of polymerization plotted against the concentration of components

FIG. 6 The structural diagram with excess of diepoxide

FIG. 7 Theoretical and experimental results of gel and sol fractions analysis. Curve 1- the concentration of pure diepoxide in the sol. Curve 2- the concentration of epoxide ends in the gel

FIG. 8 The diagram of stretched network

FIG. 9 Dependence of viscoelastic modulus on the component concentration

FIG.10 The viscoelastic modulus plot against diluent concentration

FIG.11 Viscoelastic modulus plotted against number average M_n (1) and weight average degrees of cyclic polymerization

FIG.12 Dependence of glass modulus on the component concentration

FIG.13 Glass temperature plotted against the concentration of epoxide ends in the network

FIG.14 Schematical representation of the mechanism of the reaction between diepoxides and aromatic amines

FIG.15 Scheme of possible reactions between diepoxide and amine

FIG.16 The morphology of cured epoxy matrix of different distances from the glass surfaces
 a- 2 μm b- 10 μm c- 16 μm d- 22 μm

FIG.17 Effect of curing time on composite properties

FIG.18 The scheme of a method of adhesion strength measurement

FIG.19 Kinetics of adhesion bond formation in the diepoxide reaction with aromatic amine (at 110°C):

1- Conversion 2- Adhesion strength